

Almost all tripartite pure states are uniquely determined by two overlapping marginals

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Abstract

In many-body quantum physics, the global state encodes all correlations, but the information most naturally available is often local. This makes it important to understand when a small collection of reduced density matrices already fixes the whole state. Such uniqueness questions are especially important for tomography and for the study of entanglement, because agreement with local data from a pure state does not by itself exclude a different mixed global state. We prove a generic uniqueness theorem for finite-dimensional tripartite systems. Let H_A, H_B, H_C be complex Hilbert spaces with $\dim H_A \geq 2$, and consider pure states on $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$. Then almost every such pure state is uniquely determined among all states by the two overlapping two-party marginals AB and AC . Previous results were restricted either to uniqueness against pure competitors or to uniqueness against all competitors under stronger dimension assumptions or balanced subsystem dimensions. Our result removes both restrictions.

1 Introduction

Many questions in quantum physics turn on the relation between local observations and a global state. A state on a composite system is the object that carries the full pattern of quantum correlations, yet experiments and effective descriptions often access only selected subsystems. Reduced density matrices are therefore the natural local data from which one asks whether the global quantum state can be inferred.

This issue appears in quantum tomography, in the study of entanglement, and in the analysis of many-body systems. Full tomography of a large density matrix is expensive because the number of parameters grows rapidly with the dimension of the Hilbert space. Pure states have fewer degrees of freedom, so it is natural to ask whether local marginals may already contain enough information to identify a generic pure state. The answer depends on what kinds of alternative states are allowed.

There are two relevant notions of uniqueness. A pure state is uniquely determined among pure states, or UDP, if no other pure state gives the same measurement data. It is uniquely determined among all states, or UDA, if no density matrix at all, pure or mixed, gives the same data. UDA is the stronger notion and is the more robust target for tomography, since a source intended to prepare a pure state may still have mixed noise or hidden correlations.

This work studies the tripartite system $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$. For a unit vector $\psi \in H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$, suppose that the available data are the two overlapping two-party marginals $\rho_{AB} = \text{Tr}_C |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ and $\rho_{AC} = \text{Tr}_B |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$. They share the subsystem A . The question is whether these two marginals force the global density matrix to be $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$.

The condition $\dim H_A \geq 2$ should not be viewed as a special or restrictive dimension assumption. It only excludes the case $\dim H_A = 1$. In that case the system is effectively bipartite, and the data

Work	Setting	Guarantee
Diósi [1]	$\dim H_A \geq 2$	UDP
Chen et al. [2]	$\dim H_A \geq \min(\dim H_B, \dim H_C)$	UDA
Huang et al. [3]	$\dim H_A \geq 2$ & $\dim H_B = \dim H_C$	UDA
Ours	$\dim H_A \geq 2$	UDA

Table 1: Comparison with previous uniqueness results for the marginals AB and AC .

reduce to the two one-party marginals of a pure state on $H_B \otimes H_C$. Such data do not generically fix the relative phases in a Schmidt decomposition. Thus $\dim H_A \geq 2$ is the threshold at which this becomes a genuinely tripartite marginal problem centered on the overlap A .

Theorem 1 (Main theorem, informal). *If $\dim H_A \geq 2$, then almost every pure state on $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ is uniquely determined among all states by its two marginals on AB and AC .*

Relevant previous results leave a clear path to the present question. Diósi proved that, when $\dim H_A \geq 2$, almost all tripartite pure states are UDP by the two marginals AB and AC [1]. This gives the right dimension threshold for uniqueness among pure states, but it does not exclude mixed competitors. Chen et al. later emphasized the distinction between UDP and UDA and showed that the two notions can differ in tomography [2]. In the same tripartite marginal setting, they proved UDA under the stronger sufficient condition $\dim H_A \geq \min(\dim H_B, \dim H_C)$, and noted the remaining gap between this UDA condition and the Diósi UDP threshold.

Huang et al. proved another important UDA result for generic pure states [3]. Their tripartite theorem applies to $\mathbb{C}^p \otimes \mathbb{C}^d \otimes \mathbb{C}^d$ with $p \geq 2$, so it gives UDA by the two overlapping marginals in the balanced case where the second and third subsystem dimensions are equal. They also use this to obtain a many-party qudit tomography result with only two large marginals. The remaining issue for the present tripartite problem is that the balanced condition $\dim H_B = \dim H_C$ does not cover arbitrary finite dimensions of H_B and H_C .

Our theorem closes the gap for the two overlapping marginals AB and AC . The generic threshold for UDA is the same as the generic threshold for UDP. Since UDA always implies UDP, the result shows that for this tripartite marginal problem the distinction between pure competitors and mixed competitors disappears almost everywhere. The comparison is summarized in Table 1.

This has a direct interpretation for tomography. For a generic pure state, knowing the two local states on AB and AC is not merely enough to identify the intended wavefunction within the class of pure states. It is enough to rule out every other global density matrix. Thus the overlap subsystem A , once it has dimension at least two, carries enough shared information for the two local views to determine the global state generically.

2 Preliminaries

Throughout, all vector spaces are finite-dimensional over \mathbb{C} .

2.1 Notations

A finite-dimensional complex Hilbert space H is a complex vector space with an inner product $\langle x|y\rangle$. A linear operator $T : H \rightarrow H$ has an adjoint T^\dagger , defined by

$$\langle x|Ty\rangle = \langle T^\dagger x|y\rangle \quad \text{for all } x, y \in H.$$

The operator is Hermitian if $T = T^\dagger$. It is positive semidefinite, written $T \geq 0$, if $\langle x|Tx \rangle \geq 0$ for every $x \in H$. The trace of a matrix T is independent of the choice of basis.

A density matrix, or quantum state, on H is an operator $\rho : H \rightarrow H$ such that

$$\rho \geq 0, \quad \text{Tr}(\rho) = 1.$$

A unit vector $\psi \in H$ defines the rank-one projector

$$|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| : x \mapsto \psi \langle\psi|x\rangle.$$

In matrix notation this is $\psi\psi^\dagger$. Such a density matrix is called a pure state. Two unit vectors differing by a global phase define the same pure state:

$$|e^{i\theta}\psi\rangle\langle e^{i\theta}\psi| = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|.$$

2.2 Tensor products and partial trace

If H_A, H_B, H_C are Hilbert spaces, their tensor product $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ models a tripartite quantum system. Fix orthonormal bases

$$\{|i\rangle_A\}_{i=1}^a, \quad \{|j\rangle_B\}_{j=1}^b, \quad \{|k\rangle_C\}_{k=1}^c,$$

where

$$a = \dim H_A, \quad b = \dim H_B, \quad c = \dim H_C.$$

Every vector $\psi \in H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ can be written uniquely as

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{k=1}^c c_{ijk} |i\rangle_A |j\rangle_B |k\rangle_C. \quad (1)$$

The partial trace discards one subsystem. For a density matrix ρ on $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$, its marginal on AB is

$$\rho_{AB} = \text{Tr}_C(\rho),$$

which is the unique operator on $H_A \otimes H_B$ satisfying

$$\text{Tr}(X_{AB} \rho_{AB}) = \text{Tr}((X_{AB} \otimes \mathbf{1}_C)\rho)$$

for every operator X_{AB} on $H_A \otimes H_B$. Similarly $\rho_{AC} = \text{Tr}_B(\rho)$.

Let ψ have coefficients c_{ijk} as in Eq. (1). Then $\rho_{AB} = \text{Tr}_C |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ and $\rho_{AC} = \text{Tr}_B |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ have matrix entries

$$\langle i, j | \rho_{AB} | i', j' \rangle = \sum_{k=1}^c c_{ijk} \overline{c_{i'j'k}}, \quad (2)$$

$$\langle i, k | \rho_{AC} | i', k' \rangle = \sum_{j=1}^b c_{ijk} \overline{c_{i'jk'}}. \quad (3)$$

2.3 UDP and UDA for two marginals

Definition 1. Let ψ be a unit vector in $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$.

- (a) ψ is uniquely determined among pure states, or UDP, by the two marginals AB and AC if every unit vector ϕ on $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ satisfying

$$\mathrm{Tr}_C |\phi\rangle\langle\phi| = \mathrm{Tr}_C |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|, \quad \mathrm{Tr}_B |\phi\rangle\langle\phi| = \mathrm{Tr}_B |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$$

has $|\phi\rangle\langle\phi| = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$.

- (b) ψ is uniquely determined among all states, or UDA, by the two marginals AB and AC if every density matrix σ on $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ satisfying

$$\mathrm{Tr}_C \sigma = \mathrm{Tr}_C |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|, \quad \mathrm{Tr}_B \sigma = \mathrm{Tr}_B |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$$

has $\sigma = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$.

UDA always implies UDP, because pure states are a special case of all states. The converse is generally false for arbitrary tomography problems. The theorem proved in this work says that the converse holds almost everywhere for the two-marginal tripartite problem once $\dim H_A \geq 2$.

The unit sphere in $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C \cong \mathbb{C}^{abc}$ carries the usual surface measure obtained from Lebesgue measure on \mathbb{R}^{2abc} . A property holds for *almost all* pure states if the set of unit vectors for which it fails has surface measure zero. Equivalently, one may choose the coefficients c_{ijk} from any probability distribution with a density on \mathbb{C}^{abc} and then normalize the vector. A property that fails only on a subset of coefficient space with Lebesgue measure zero then holds almost surely after normalization.

3 Finite-dimensional tools

3.1 Purifications and uniqueness of purifications

Definition 2 (Purification). Let ρ_X be a density matrix on a Hilbert space H_X . A purification of ρ_X is a unit vector $\Phi \in H_X \otimes H_E$, for some auxiliary Hilbert space H_E , such that

$$\mathrm{Tr}_E |\Phi\rangle\langle\Phi| = \rho_X.$$

Lemma 1 (Uniqueness of purification up to an isometry). Let $\Psi \in H_X \otimes H_Y$ and $\Phi \in H_X \otimes H_Z$ be unit vectors such that

$$\mathrm{Tr}_Y |\Psi\rangle\langle\Psi| = \mathrm{Tr}_Z |\Phi\rangle\langle\Phi|.$$

Let $S \subseteq H_Y$ be the support of $\mathrm{Tr}_X |\Psi\rangle\langle\Psi|$. Then there is an isometry $V : S \rightarrow H_Z$ such that

$$\Phi = (\mathbf{1}_X \otimes V)\Psi.$$

If desired, after enlarging H_Z or defining V arbitrarily on S^\perp , the isometry may be regarded as defined on all of H_Y .

3.2 A fixed-point theorem for completely positive maps

For a positive definite matrix $R > 0$, the functional

$$\omega_R(T) = \text{Tr}(RT)$$

is faithful on positive semidefinite matrices in the sense that if $P \geq 0$ and $\omega_R(P) = 0$, then $P = 0$.

Lemma 2 (Kadison–Schwarz inequality). *Let*

$$\Lambda(T) = \sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} T L_{\alpha}$$

be a unital completely positive map on $M_r(\mathbb{C})$, meaning

$$\sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} L_{\alpha} = \mathbf{1}_r.$$

Then, for every $Z \in M_r(\mathbb{C})$,

$$\Lambda(Z^{\dagger} Z) \geq \Lambda(Z)^{\dagger} \Lambda(Z).$$

Lemma 3. *Let Λ be as in Lemma 2. Suppose $Z \in M_r(\mathbb{C})$ satisfies both*

$$\Lambda(Z^{\dagger} Z) = \Lambda(Z)^{\dagger} \Lambda(Z), \quad \Lambda(Z Z^{\dagger}) = \Lambda(Z) \Lambda(Z)^{\dagger}.$$

Then, for every $S \in M_r(\mathbb{C})$,

$$\Lambda(ZS) = \Lambda(Z) \Lambda(S), \quad \Lambda(SZ) = \Lambda(S) \Lambda(Z).$$

Proof. Use the isometry V from the proof of Lemma 2. Equality in the first Kadison–Schwarz inequality says

$$V^{\dagger}(Z^{\dagger} \otimes \mathbf{1})(I - VV^{\dagger})(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})V = 0.$$

The operator on the left is $Y^{\dagger}Y$ with $Y = (I - VV^{\dagger})(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})V$, so $Y = 0$. Thus

$$(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})V = VV^{\dagger}(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})V.$$

If also $\Lambda(Z) = Z_0$, then $V^{\dagger}(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})V = Z_0$, and the preceding equality gives

$$(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})V = VZ_0. \tag{4}$$

Equality in the second Kadison–Schwarz inequality applied to Z^{\dagger} gives

$$(Z^{\dagger} \otimes \mathbf{1})V = V\Lambda(Z^{\dagger}) = VZ_0^{\dagger}. \tag{5}$$

Taking the adjoint of Eq. (5) yields

$$V^{\dagger}(Z \otimes \mathbf{1}) = Z_0V^{\dagger}. \tag{6}$$

Now compute, for any S ,

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda(ZS) &= V^{\dagger}(ZS \otimes \mathbf{1})V \\ &= V^{\dagger}(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})(S \otimes \mathbf{1})V \\ &= Z_0V^{\dagger}(S \otimes \mathbf{1})V \\ &= \Lambda(Z)\Lambda(S), \end{aligned}$$

where Eq. (6) was used. Similarly, using Eq. (4),

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda(SZ) &= V^\dagger(S \otimes \mathbf{1})(Z \otimes \mathbf{1})V \\ &= V^\dagger(S \otimes \mathbf{1})VZ_0 \\ &= \Lambda(S)\Lambda(Z).\end{aligned}$$

□

Proposition 1 (Fixed points with a faithful invariant state). *Let*

$$\Lambda(T) = \sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} T L_{\alpha}$$

be a unital completely positive map on $M_r(\mathbb{C})$:

$$\sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} L_{\alpha} = \mathbf{1}_r.$$

Assume there exists a positive definite matrix $R > 0$ such that

$$\sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha} R L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} = R. \quad (*)$$

Then the fixed-point set

$$\text{Fix}(\Lambda) = \{T \in M_r(\mathbb{C}) : \Lambda(T) = T\}$$

is a unital $$ -subalgebra of $M_r(\mathbb{C})$. Moreover, if $A \in \text{Fix}(\Lambda)$ and the smallest unital $*$ -subalgebra containing A is all of $M_r(\mathbb{C})$, then Λ is the identity map. In that case every Kraus operator L_{α} is a scalar multiple of the identity.*

Proof. Define $\omega(T) = \text{Tr}(RT)$. Condition (*) says ω is invariant under Λ :

$$\begin{aligned}\omega(\Lambda(T)) &= \text{Tr}\left(R \sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} T L_{\alpha}\right) \\ &= \text{Tr}\left(\sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha} R L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} T\right) \\ &= \text{Tr}(RT) = \omega(T).\end{aligned}$$

Let $Z \in \text{Fix}(\Lambda)$. Lemma 2 gives

$$P := \Lambda(Z^{\dagger}Z) - Z^{\dagger}Z \geq 0.$$

Applying ω and using invariance,

$$\omega(P) = \omega(\Lambda(Z^{\dagger}Z)) - \omega(Z^{\dagger}Z) = 0.$$

Since $R > 0$, ω is faithful on positive matrices, so $P = 0$. Hence

$$\Lambda(Z^{\dagger}Z) = Z^{\dagger}Z.$$

The same argument applied to ZZ^{\dagger} gives

$$\Lambda(ZZ^{\dagger}) = ZZ^{\dagger}.$$

Thus the hypotheses of Lemma 3 hold, and for every $S \in \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})$,

$$\Lambda(ZS) = Z\Lambda(S), \quad \Lambda(SZ) = \Lambda(S)Z. \quad (7)$$

Also $Z^\dagger \in \text{Fix}(\Lambda)$ because

$$\Lambda(Z^\dagger) = \sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} Z^{\dagger} L_{\alpha} = \left(\sum_{\alpha} L_{\alpha}^{\dagger} Z L_{\alpha} \right)^{\dagger} = Z^{\dagger}.$$

Now let $Z, W \in \text{Fix}(\Lambda)$. Taking $S = W$ in Eq. (7) gives

$$\Lambda(ZW) = Z\Lambda(W) = ZW,$$

so $ZW \in \text{Fix}(\Lambda)$. The identity is fixed because Λ is unital. Therefore $\text{Fix}(\Lambda)$ is a unital $*$ -subalgebra.

If $A \in \text{Fix}(\Lambda)$ and the unital $*$ -algebra generated by A is all of $\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})$, then the fixed-point algebra contains all of $\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})$. Hence $\Lambda(T) = T$ for every T , so Λ is the identity map. \square

3.3 Single-matrix generation of a full matrix algebra

For $A \in \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})$, let $C^*(A)$ denote the smallest unital $*$ -subalgebra of $\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})$ containing A . Equivalently, $C^*(A)$ is the set of all finite linear combinations of finite products made from A , A^\dagger , and the identity.

Lemma 4. *For each $r \geq 1$, the set*

$$\mathcal{G}_r = \{A \in \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C}) : C^*(A) = \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})\}$$

has full Lebesgue measure in $\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C}) \cong \mathbb{R}^{2r^2}$.

Proof. For $r = 1$ the assertion is immediate. Assume $r \geq 2$, and write

$$\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})_{\text{sa}} = \{T \in \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C}) : T = T^\dagger\}.$$

By [4, Lemma 3.10], the set

$$\mathcal{B}_r = \{(H, K) \in \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})_{\text{sa}} \times \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})_{\text{sa}} : C^*(H, K) \neq \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})\}$$

has Lebesgue measure zero in the real vector space $\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})_{\text{sa}} \times \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})_{\text{sa}}$, where $C^*(H, K)$ denotes the smallest unital $*$ -subalgebra of $\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})$ containing both H and K .

Consider the real-linear isomorphism

$$\Phi : \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C}) \longrightarrow \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})_{\text{sa}} \times \mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C})_{\text{sa}}, \quad \Phi(A) = \left(\frac{A + A^\dagger}{2}, \frac{A - A^\dagger}{2i} \right).$$

Its inverse is $(H, K) \mapsto H + iK$. If $\Phi(A) = (H, K)$, then

$$A = H + iK, \quad A^\dagger = H - iK.$$

Hence $H, K \in C^*(A)$ and $A \in C^*(H, K)$, so

$$C^*(A) = C^*(H, K).$$

Therefore

$$\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \mathcal{G}_r = \Phi^{-1}(\mathcal{B}_r).$$

Since $\Phi^{-1}(\mathcal{B}_r)$ has Lebesgue measure zero in $\mathbf{M}_r(\mathbb{C}) \cong \mathbb{R}^{2r^2}$, \mathcal{G}_r has full Lebesgue measure. \square

We now convert a tripartite vector into matrices. This is the bridge between reduced density matrices and the fixed-point theorem.

Let ψ be written as in Eq. (1). For each $i \in \{1, \dots, a\}$ define the $b \times c$ coefficient slice

$$C_i \in \mathbb{M}_{b \times c}(\mathbb{C}), \quad (C_i)_{jk} = c_{ijk}. \quad (8)$$

Thus C_i is the BC coefficient matrix of ψ when the A index is fixed to i .

Lemma 5. *Assume $a \geq 2$ and $c \leq b$. For almost every vector $\psi \in H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$, the first slice C_1 has full column rank c , and the matrix*

$$A = (C_1^\dagger C_1)^{-1/2} C_1^\dagger C_2 (C_1^\dagger C_1)^{-1/2} \in \mathbb{M}_c(\mathbb{C}) \quad (9)$$

generates the full matrix algebra $\mathbb{M}_c(\mathbb{C})$ as a unital $$ -algebra.*

Proof. The set of $b \times c$ matrices that fail to have full column rank is the common zero set of all $c \times c$ minors. Since $c \leq b$, at least one such minor is not the zero polynomial, so this rank-deficient set has Lebesgue measure zero. Thus $C_1^\dagger C_1$ is positive definite for almost every C_1 .

Fix C_1 with full column rank. The linear map

$$C_2 \mapsto C_1^\dagger C_2$$

from $\mathbb{M}_{b \times c}(\mathbb{C})$ onto $\mathbb{M}_c(\mathbb{C})$ is surjective: given any $Y \in \mathbb{M}_c(\mathbb{C})$, choosing

$$C_2 = C_1 (C_1^\dagger C_1)^{-1} Y$$

gives $C_1^\dagger C_2 = Y$. Multiplication on the left and right by the fixed invertible matrix $(C_1^\dagger C_1)^{-1/2}$ is an invertible linear change of coordinates on $\mathbb{M}_c(\mathbb{C})$. Therefore, for this fixed C_1 , the set of C_2 for which the matrix A in Eq. (9) fails to lie in \mathcal{G}_c is the preimage of a measure-zero set under a surjective linear map, and hence has measure zero. By Fubini's theorem, the bad pairs (C_1, C_2) have measure zero. The remaining coefficient slices C_3, \dots, C_a are unrestricted, so the bad set in the full coefficient space also has measure zero. \square

4 Main result

Theorem 2. *Let H_A, H_B, H_C be finite-dimensional complex Hilbert spaces with*

$$\dim H_A = a \geq 2, \quad \dim H_B = b \geq 1, \quad \dim H_C = c \geq 1.$$

Then, for almost every unit vector $\psi \in H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$, if σ is any density matrix on $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ satisfying

$$\mathrm{Tr}_C \sigma = \mathrm{Tr}_C |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|, \quad \mathrm{Tr}_B \sigma = \mathrm{Tr}_B |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|,$$

then

$$\sigma = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|.$$

Equivalently, almost every such ψ is UDA by the two reduced density matrices on AB and AC .

Proof. Because the two marginals AB and AC are interchanged by swapping the labels B and C , it is enough to prove the theorem when $c \leq b$. Assume therefore that $c \leq b$. By Lemma 5, it is enough to prove UDA for every unit vector ψ satisfying the following two conditions:

(G1) C_1 has full column rank c .

(G2) The matrix

$$A = (C_1^\dagger C_1)^{-1/2} C_1^\dagger C_2 (C_1^\dagger C_1)^{-1/2}$$

generates $M_c(\mathbb{C})$ as a unital $*$ -algebra.

Fix such a unit vector ψ .

Let σ be a density matrix with the same AB and AC marginals as $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$. Choose a purification

$$\Phi \in H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C \otimes H_E$$

of σ , so that

$$\text{Tr}_E |\Phi\rangle\langle\Phi| = \sigma.$$

Then

$$\text{Tr}_{CE} |\Phi\rangle\langle\Phi| = \text{Tr}_C \sigma = \text{Tr}_C |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|.$$

Thus Φ and ψ are two purifications of the same AB state. Since C_1 has full column rank, the C marginal of $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ is full rank on H_C : indeed, using the convention $(C_i)_{jk} = c_{ijk}$,

$$\langle k | \rho_C | k' \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b c_{ijk} \overline{c_{ijk'}}, \quad \rho_C^T = \sum_{i=1}^a C_i^\dagger C_i \geq C_1^\dagger C_1 > 0.$$

Since transposition preserves positive definiteness, $\rho_C > 0$. Therefore Lemma 1 gives an isometry

$$V : H_C \rightarrow H_C \otimes H_E$$

such that

$$\Phi = (\mathbf{1}_{AB} \otimes V) \psi. \tag{10}$$

Likewise,

$$\text{Tr}_{BE} |\Phi\rangle\langle\Phi| = \text{Tr}_B \sigma = \text{Tr}_B |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|.$$

Thus Φ and ψ are two purifications of the same AC state. Again by Lemma 1, after extending an isometry from the support of the B marginal to all of H_B if necessary, there is an isometry

$$W : H_B \rightarrow H_B \otimes H_E$$

such that

$$\Phi = (\mathbf{1}_{AC} \otimes W) \psi. \tag{11}$$

If the two applications of the purification lemma initially use different auxiliary spaces, replace both by a common larger space and append zero components, so that Eqs. (10) and (11) are unaffected.

Choose an orthonormal basis $\{|e\rangle\}$ of H_E . Write

$$V|k\rangle_C = \sum_{\ell, e} (V_e)_{\ell k} |\ell\rangle_C |e\rangle, \quad W|j\rangle_B = \sum_{m, e} (W_e)_{mj} |m\rangle_B |e\rangle,$$

where $V_e \in M_c(\mathbb{C})$ and $W_e \in M_b(\mathbb{C})$. Since V and W are isometries,

$$\sum_e V_e^\dagger V_e = \mathbf{1}_c, \quad \sum_e W_e^\dagger W_e = \mathbf{1}_b. \tag{12}$$

Equating the coefficients of the same vector Φ in Eqs. (10) and (11), for each i and each e we obtain

$$W_e C_i = C_i X_e, \quad X_e := V_e^T \in M_c(\mathbb{C}). \quad (13)$$

Indeed, the (m, ℓ) entry of the left side is $\sum_j (W_e)_{mj} c_{ij\ell}$, while the (m, ℓ) entry of the right side is $\sum_k c_{imk} (V_e)_{\ell k}$, exactly the equality of the coefficient of $|i\rangle_A |m\rangle_B |\ell\rangle_C |e\rangle$.

From $\sum_e V_e^\dagger V_e = \mathbf{1}_c$ and $X_e = V_e^T$ we get

$$\sum_e X_e X_e^\dagger = \mathbf{1}_c. \quad (14)$$

Now set

$$R = C_1^\dagger C_1 > 0, \quad G = C_1^\dagger C_2. \quad (15)$$

Using Eq. (13) and the second identity in Eq. (12), we compute

$$\begin{aligned} R &= C_1^\dagger C_1 = C_1^\dagger \left(\sum_e W_e^\dagger W_e \right) C_1 \\ &= \sum_e (W_e C_1)^\dagger (W_e C_1) = \sum_e (C_1 X_e)^\dagger (C_1 X_e) \\ &= \sum_e X_e^\dagger R X_e. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} G &= C_1^\dagger C_2 = C_1^\dagger \left(\sum_e W_e^\dagger W_e \right) C_2 \\ &= \sum_e (W_e C_1)^\dagger (W_e C_2) = \sum_e (C_1 X_e)^\dagger (C_2 X_e) \\ &= \sum_e X_e^\dagger G X_e. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Define

$$L_e = R^{1/2} X_e R^{-1/2}. \quad (18)$$

Then Eq. (16) gives

$$\sum_e L_e^\dagger L_e = R^{-1/2} \left(\sum_e X_e^\dagger R X_e \right) R^{-1/2} = \mathbf{1}_c. \quad (19)$$

Also Eq. (14) gives the faithful invariant state condition

$$\sum_e L_e R L_e^\dagger = R^{1/2} \left(\sum_e X_e X_e^\dagger \right) R^{1/2} = R. \quad (20)$$

Consider the unital completely positive map

$$\Lambda(T) = \sum_e L_e^\dagger T L_e \quad (T \in M_c(\mathbb{C})).$$

Let

$$A = R^{-1/2} G R^{-1/2}.$$

By Eq. (17),

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda(A) &= \sum_e R^{-1/2} X_e^\dagger R^{1/2} (R^{-1/2} G R^{-1/2}) R^{1/2} X_e R^{-1/2} \\ &= R^{-1/2} \left(\sum_e X_e^\dagger G X_e \right) R^{-1/2} \\ &= R^{-1/2} G R^{-1/2} = A.\end{aligned}$$

By the generic condition (G2), A generates the full algebra $M_c(\mathbb{C})$. Equations (19) and (20) are the hypotheses of Proposition 1. Hence Λ is the identity map and every L_e is a scalar multiple of $\mathbf{1}_c$:

$$L_e = \alpha_e \mathbf{1}_c.$$

By Eq. (18), this implies

$$X_e = R^{-1/2} L_e R^{1/2} = \alpha_e \mathbf{1}_c.$$

Since $X_e = V_e^T$, we also have

$$V_e = \alpha_e \mathbf{1}_c.$$

Thus

$$V|k\rangle_C = \sum_e \alpha_e |k\rangle_C |e\rangle = |k\rangle_C \otimes \eta_E, \quad \eta_E = \sum_e \alpha_e |e\rangle.$$

The isometry condition gives $\|\eta_E\| = 1$. Therefore V is the trivial isometry

$$Vx = x \otimes \eta_E \quad (x \in H_C).$$

Using Eq. (10),

$$\Phi = (\mathbf{1}_{AB} \otimes V)\psi = \psi \otimes \eta_E.$$

Finally,

$$\sigma = \text{Tr}_E |\Phi\rangle\langle\Phi| = \text{Tr}_E (|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| \otimes |\eta\rangle\langle\eta|) = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|.$$

This proves UDA for every vector satisfying (G1) and (G2). Those conditions hold almost everywhere by Lemma 5, so the theorem is proved when $c \leq b$. Interchanging B and C proves the case $b \leq c$. \square

Corollary 1. *For tripartite systems $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ with $\dim H_A \geq 2$, almost every pure state is UDA by AB and AC .*

Remark 1. *When $\dim H_A = 1$, the problem is bipartite: one is trying to reconstruct a pure state on $H_B \otimes H_C$ from its two one-party marginals. Take $H_B = H_C = \mathbb{C}^2$. A full-measure set of two-qubit pure states has Schmidt rank two and unequal Schmidt coefficients, so such a state can be written as*

$$\varphi = \sqrt{p}|b_0\rangle|c_0\rangle + \sqrt{1-p}|b_1\rangle|c_1\rangle, \quad 0 < p < 1, \quad p \neq \frac{1}{2},$$

for orthonormal bases $\{b_0, b_1\}$ and $\{c_0, c_1\}$. For each real phase θ , define

$$\varphi_\theta = \sqrt{p}|b_0\rangle|c_0\rangle + e^{i\theta} \sqrt{1-p}|b_1\rangle|c_1\rangle.$$

The cross terms vanish under either one-party partial trace, so

$$\text{Tr}_C |\varphi_\theta\rangle\langle\varphi_\theta| = p|b_0\rangle\langle b_0| + (1-p)|b_1\rangle\langle b_1|$$

and

$$\text{Tr}_B |\varphi_\theta\rangle\langle\varphi_\theta| = p|c_0\rangle\langle c_0| + (1-p)|c_1\rangle\langle c_1|,$$

which are independent of θ . Therefore one-party marginals do not generically identify a bipartite pure state.

Remark 2. *The theorem is an almost-all theorem, not an all-states theorem. The distinction is necessary. In the three-qubit case, the GHZ-type vectors*

$$\psi_\theta = a|000\rangle + be^{i\theta}|111\rangle, \quad |a|^2 + |b|^2 = 1,$$

have two-body marginals independent of the phase θ . Such states cannot be UDP, hence cannot be UDA. They lie in the measure-zero exceptional set excluded by the genericity conditions in Lemma 5.

5 Conclusion

We showed that two overlapping marginals AB and AC determine almost every pure state on a finite-dimensional tripartite system $H_A \otimes H_B \otimes H_C$ among all density matrices whenever $\dim H_A \geq 2$. Equivalently, almost every such pure state is UDA by these two marginals. The result shows that the information contained in two overlapping pair marginals is stronger than pure-state uniqueness. It rules out not only other pure states, but also every mixed density matrix with the same local data. Therefore, for the marginals AB and AC , the UDP and UDA thresholds coincide. In this sense, overlapping marginals provide a minimal and robust route from local data to the determination of the global state.

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